

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING “DESCRIPTIVE GEOMETRY”

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Annotation: The article discusses the modern capabilities of computer technology in teaching descriptive geometry. The ways of widespread use of modern information technologies are described, allowing the introduction of new methods and forms of teaching into the teaching process.

Key words: descriptive geometry, technical drawing, drawing, graphic design, geometric object, spatial imagination.

In the training of technical specialists, the study of descriptive geometry is important. Descriptive geometry methods are the theoretical basis for solving technical drawing problems.

In technology, drawings are the main means of expressing human ideas. When determining the shape and size of objects, they should be quite simple and accurate in graphic design, helping to comprehensively examine the depicted objects. To correctly express your thoughts using a drawing, you need knowledge of the theoretical foundations of constructing images of geometric objects, their diversity and the relationships between them, which is the subject of descriptive geometry.

In addition, the study of descriptive geometry contributes to the development of students' spatial concepts and spatial imagination [1] – qualities that characterize a high level of engineering thinking and are necessary for solving applied problems. In the process of studying descriptive geometry, other goals are achieved, the general scientific horizons of students are expanded, logical thinking skills, attentiveness, independence, observation, accuracy and other qualities are developed, the development of which is one of the tasks of training and education in a higher technical school.

When studying descriptive geometry, first we consider not some specific objects, but abstract points, straight lines and planes, which requires a corresponding restructuring of the students' thinking. The drawing in descriptive geometry occupies a leading position, and it is performed not in axonometric, but in orthogonal projections and requires certain mental efforts to understand.

A particular difficulty for most students is the mental representation of spatial figures, and many sections of the discipline are directly related to three-dimensional images. Since descriptive geometry studies the shape, size and relative position of

various geometric objects in space, an important aspect of its study is the principle of clarity.

Lately, computer graphics are the most visual and effective means of presenting information [2]. Visualization of educational material using graphic packages provides great assistance in the perception and understanding of the material being studied, allows students to present and understand complex theoretical material on descriptive geometry, and improve the level of their graphic training [3]. The greatest efficiency comes from the use of three-dimensional computer graphics [4, 5]. Showing electronic slides with three-dimensional models helps to increase students' awareness of the display of various spatial objects on a plane and the development of their spatial thinking [1]. Three-dimensional graphics are widely used in solving descriptive geometry problems when projecting spatial geometric objects onto projection planes (Fig. 1, 2). Using animation effects, you can demonstrate the sequence of their projection and more clearly examine the relative position of various geometric objects in space. For a better perception of the material, you can simultaneously show both a spatial model of a geometric object and its complex drawing (Fig. 1, 2). When studying descriptive geometry, graphic material can be demonstrated in large quantities. This allows you to make the lesson more interesting, and the material more accessible and memorable.

Figure 1. Constructing a horizontal line

Figure 2. Front plane of the level

With the help of modern computer technologies, it is possible to present a step-by-step solution to a problem in dynamics. For example, Figure 3 shows a step-by-step construction of the line of greatest inclination of the plane of triangle ABC to the horizontal projection plane.

Performing actions in solving certain problems in dynamics increases the ease of perception of multi-stage geometric constructions. All auxiliary constructions that characterize the progress of solving the problem can be hidden, which will make the drawing easier to read, and also restored in order to follow the logic and check the correctness of the completed image.

Figure 3. Construction of the line of greatest slope

Simplicity and clarity are the main features of the developed methodological illustrative material. Without deviating from the traditional method of presenting graphic information, visualization of educational material is carried out using modern information technologies [2].

The advantages of electronic publications are their mobility, accessibility of communication with the development of computer networks, and constant updating of information material. The use of electronic textbooks provides the opportunity to obtain any information in various accessible forms, most suitable in each specific case and taking into account the individual abilities of students.

Modern computer technologies make it possible to introduce interactive three-dimensional models into the electronic publication (Fig. 4) [4]. The spatial model can be viewed from any side, turning and rotating it; to identify internal outlines and fully identify the shape, you can make any section of the 3-D model by setting the position of the cutting plane, all this equips students with specific ideas about geometric shapes.

Figure 4. Interactive 3D model in the electronic textbook

The visibility and interactivity of the electronic publication can significantly increase students' interest in the discipline being studied, the level of orientation on the topic and the degree of mastery of the material.

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